

IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ARABIC

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Annotation: Learning a new language, especially Arabic, can have a number of great benefits. It's good for our mental acuity, it's good for our communication skills, and it's good for our awareness of other cultures and world history. The purpose of this scientific work is to show the reasons for the importance of learning the Arabic language.

Key words: educational matter, Arabic dialects, the Qur'an and Sunnah, international conferences, cognitive and intellectual benefits.

Obviously, English is the most widely used language in educational matters worldwide. For this reason, the Arabic language is widely used and studied. The reason for learning Arabic in the modern world is because it is a source of global communication with one-third of the world's population, who are Arabs. In addition, Arabic is the fourth most spoken language.

This will help you to know the importance of Arabic and the reasons to learn Arabic. After reading carefully, you will find strong reasons to manage your Arabic language learning.

In order to become a Muslim, one must learn Arabic in order to effectively learn the Qur'an and Sunnah.

Arabic is the best Semitic language worldwide. It is spoken as a first language by about 300 million people in more than twenty-five countries. Because of this, many other people consider it as a language. More than 100 million people use it as a second language, and almost as many people use it as a foreign language.

Since the Arabic language has been used by different countries based on

history, many Arabic dialects have emerged with differences in spelling and vocabulary. Accordingly, if you want to learn Arabic online, there are three main Arabic dialects that you need to know:

I Quran or classical Arabic. The first subtlety is the language of the Qur'an. It originated from Makkah, that is, the place where the Qur'an was revealed by the Prophet (pbuh). If you want to understand the Qur'an in Arabic, you should focus on learning the Arabic language of the Qur'an.

II Modern Standard Arabic. "This fixed sensitivity is additional legislation on community and official platforms such as radio, television, mosques, books, newspapers and international conferences."

III Colloquial Arabic dialects. The third life delicacy belongs to the Arabic language, which the Arabs acquired in the diary.

Learning Arabic, it can open many new opportunities for you personally and professionally. The following are the main reasons:

1. You can stay connected in a distant world

The number of people interested in learning a second language has increased dramatically in the past two years amid all the restrictions. Reason: At a time when travel is so limited, learning Arabic or other languages has become the best way to feel connected to the wider world. For some, it was a chance to connect with family members in another country. For others, it was all about getting to know another culture. With a strong foundation in Arabic, you can strengthen your connections with friends and family around the world.

2. Learning Arabic helps you learn other languages

Arabic is often considered a difficult language for English speakers, but once you've mastered the basics, it can be a solid foundation for other similar languages. After you have made some progress in Arabic, it will be much easier for you to learn Turkish, Persian and other languages. It doesn't take long before you start to see how many words and grammar rules have the same roots, and these similarities always make it easier to start learning a new language.

3. Companies are looking for Arabic speakers

There are many opportunities for those who speak Arabic. As the business and corporate world continues to expand into new countries, people who can speak multiple languages will be in high demand. Arabic is the main language for business in many countries, so if you want to get a job in a company with international connections, you can expect immediate attention on your resume. In addition, if you can demonstrate sufficient Arabic fluency, you may be able to earn a higher salary.

4. You can have a more satisfying travel experience

Although travel has been limited in the last few years, many places are opening up and welcoming new visitors. Egypt has been one of the biggest tourist destinations for years and there is so much to see and do that no one should miss out on. And when you arrive, imagine how enriching your experience will be when you don't have to rely on tour guides to interact with others. You can see the country from a whole new perspective.

5. You can make it a family activity

There are many benefits of learning Arabic together as a family. For starters, when you travel as a family to Arabic-speaking countries, you can all socialize with your neighbors and acquaintances. If you have family in these countries, this is a great way to introduce the rest of your family to them. On top of that, learning a second language has many cognitive and intellectual benefits, giving the young members of your family a strong start. It is important to note that if you learn Arabic as a family, you will make the whole experience more interesting. You can play games together, watch movies and shows together, and most importantly, hold each other accountable for sticking to your coursework and achieving your goals.

6. The language chosen by Allah for the Qur'an and Paradise

Allah chose the Arabic language to convey His messages to people. He published his book "Holy Qur'an" in Arabic. Allah Almighty has made the Arabic language superior to all other languages. This is one of the advantages of learning

Arabic. Of course, if Allah had willed, He would have revealed the Holy Qur'an not only in any language, but in all languages, as He said in the Holy Qur'an: "Indeed, We have sent it down as a Qur'an in Arabic, that you may understand" [12:2]

For a Muslim, this verse is reason enough to learn the Arabic language of the Qur'an.

7. Help you learn Quran and Sunnah

Whoever learns the Qur'an and the Sunnah will attain real wealth. It is important for every Muslim in Arabic to understand the words of Allah Almighty and the words of His Messenger. The benefit of learning Arabic is that one can easily gain merit for both worlds. Whoever wants to know the Qur'an and Sunnah should learn Arabic. The Qur'an, though it is in this world, is not of this world, but of the Lord of the worlds. Allah Almighty says: "The revelation of this book is from Allah, the All-Wise". Quran [39:1]

8. The way to understand Islamic sciences

It is clear that the various Islamic disciplines are clearly derived from the Arabic language disciplines, since the various concerns discussed here are linguistic issues. Understanding these issues requires a solid foundation in Arabic linguistics. These disciplines include al-Tafsir (exegesis of the Qur'an), 'Ulum al-Qur'an (Sciences of the Qur'an), 'Ilm al-Hadith, al-Fiqh (Islamic jurisprudence), al-'aqida (Islamic theology). Al-Tafsir - Analysis of the Qur'an. Al-Hadith - Analysis of Prophetic narrations. Al-Fiqh is the science of Islamic jurisprudence. Al-Aqeedah - Study of Quranic Beliefs and Sunnahs etc.

9. Develop sincerity in worshiping Allah

Knowing the Arabic language makes our devotion and praises to God more rewarding. This is especially related to the effectiveness of prayer, reading and listening to the Qur'an, lectures, supplications and the like. Simply put, knowing Arabic frees us from the need for a mediator or translator between us and God Almighty. The purpose of this life is to worship and obey God. If we learn Arabic,

we will understand the Quran more deeply. The benefit of learning Arabic is that it develops sincerity in worshipping Allah. Understanding the Arabic language brings us closer to Allah and glorification becomes more important because of the Islamic influence on its speakers. Learning Arabic is one way to learn more about Islamic culture.

Allah Almighty says about this: "O Prophet, if the sea were ink to write the words of my Lord, even if we filled it with the same amount, it would surely run out."

10. The demand for Arabic speakers is increasing in the modern world

Main of the advantages of learning Arabic is its use in economic and commercial departments. Arabic is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. Only a few people in the West know how to speak Arabic. Arabic is a great skill that will help you stand out in many great job and service opportunities. Therefore, we should pay special attention to learning Arabic for adults and children.

To sum up, God created the Qur'an in Arabic, and the duties and obligations to Muslims were explained in Arabic, the holy book was written entirely in Arabic. Therefore, every Muslim should learn to read and speak Arabic, the language of the Prophet, so that he can understand and interpret the word of God through prayer and reading the Qur'an. If we knew who God is and who His Messenger is, we would not think about learning the language of God's Book and the Sunnah of His Messenger again and again. The Qur'an and Sunnah contain so much real wealth that most of us would rather remain heedless and poor forever. However, we could become close to God and rich simply by doing the deeds mentioned in the Qur'an.

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